

The Normal and the Pathological: Frantz Fanon, Georges Canguilhem, and Colonial Fascism

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Abstract: This article unpacks Frantz Fanon’s theoretical analysis of the normal and the pathological through the French philosopher of science, Georges Canguilhem. Placing Fanon in conversation with Canguilhem I argue that, for Fanon, racism is pathological because it establishes a norm that continually constrains openness towards the future. Drawing on historical and contemporary debates on fascism, vitalism, necropolitics, and biopolitics, I show how Fanon engages with Canguilhem’s theory of the normal and the pathological to revise his account of fascism, and to generate a vital, anti-fascist, anti-colonial, politics through a volunteer army—the African Legion.

Keywords Fascism, Colonialism, Biopolitics, Race War, Fantasy

The problem of the normal and the pathological runs throughout Frantz Fanon’s work: from his early psychiatric writings as a medical student, to *Black Skin, White Masks*, to his clinical psychiatry practice in Blida, Algeria, to his revolutionary *Wretched of the Earth*. For Fanon, the definition of the “normal” was bound up with, and defined by a racist, colonial capitalist, culture: “the racist in a culture is therefore normal. He has achieved perfect harmony of economic relations and ideology.”¹ Later, Fanon remarks that racism in a colonial culture is “normal”: “Race prejudice in fact obeys a flawless logic. A country that lives, draws its substance from the exploitation of other peoples, makes those peoples inferior. Race prejudice applied to those peoples is normal.”²

The idea that racism is “normal” may seem to run against the grain of contemporary Fanon scholarship, and other moments in Fanon’s own oeuvre. For example, Achille Mbembe draws on Fanon to describe race as a “codified

madness” and a “delirium.”³ For David Marriott, Fanon shows us the ways in which “to be black... is to be originally violated by a whiteness that comes from the inside out, and this anteriority necessarily follows from an intimacy that is already perverse.”⁴ Racism is prelogical, affective, and perverse phantasy and phobia. Frank Wilderson echoes Marriott when he argues that for Fanon, Blackness is trauma, a radical incoherence and gratuitous violence.⁵ The idea that the racist is “normal” seems to contradict Fanon’s own observations on negrophobogenesis and the affective delirium that constitutes white supremacy.⁶ How are we to make sense of Fanon’s statement that racism is “normal” and, at the same time, a phobic fantasy and anxiety against life itself?

In contemporary scholarship, Fanon is often placed in conversation with Jacques Lacan, Maurice Merleau-Ponty, Jean-Paul Sartre, and, more recently, the institutional psychotherapy of François Tosquelles. This essay runs these questions through Fanon’s (often unacknowledged) debts to the French philosopher Georges Canguilhem.⁷ Understudied and under-translated, Canguilhem falls in a space between Sartre and de Beauvoir’s generation, and that of Foucault, Derrida, and Deleuze. Canguilhem had a positive influence as a teacher and mentor to some of the most famous names in French theory: Etienne Balibar, Pierre Bourdieu, and Alain Badiou. Jacques Derrida was his assistant during an early stage of his career, and Louis Althusser claimed that his “debt to Canguilhem was incalculable.”⁸ As a philosopher of science, Canguilhem’s early work questioned the relationship between the life sciences, and a philosophy of life, through an archeological method. This essay does not mean to argue that a single authoritative “Fanon” can emerge from reading Fanon alongside Canguilhem. Fanon’s influences were multiple and include institutional psychotherapy and Negritude. However, reading Fanon alongside Canguilhem on the question of the normal and the pathological illuminates a structure of Fanon’s thought on the relationship between the normal, pathological, vitalism, and fascism.

Following Canguilhem, I argue that Fanon articulates a theory of fascism that centers on the relationship of the “normal” to life and vitalism. Fanon’s theory of fascism analyzes the relationship between the normal and the pathological, and life and death, through colonial combat. Whereas Canguilhem proceeds to articulate a theory of race war through philosophy and medicine, for Fanon the lifemaking—and lifetaking—processes of racism and colonialism are part of colonial war. The fantasies and disavowals of colonial warfare constitute the normal and the pathological, racializing the colonized as a perpetual threat to the colonial norm. The colonial norm, equated with life itself, transforms colonial subjects into monstrous pathologies. The only way of protecting colonial lifemaking from the pathological and infectious deathmaking of the colonized, is to wage combat, to the point of genocide.⁹

Like Canguilhem, Fanon articulates his affirmative biopolitics by repositioning the question of life, and the relationship between the normal and the pathological. Fanon articulates this through an abnormal subject who “appeals and begs.” Tracing this figure through Fanon’s oeuvre, I argue that the

culmination of Fanon's thought is not the lumpenproletariat, but rather Fanon's vision of a Pan-African future, and a people's army institutionalized in an African Legion. Through this articulation of a dynamic future emerging through and from a popular African Legion, Fanon repositions life away from the colonial norm, and towards a new global order.

The paper proceeds in four parts. First, I unpack Canguilhem's theory of fascism, race war, and biopolitics. Second, I show how Fanon articulates a similar project in *Black Skin, White Masks* and *Dying Colonialism* through his reading of the family. Like Canguilhem, Fanon sees the "normal" and the question of life constrained and delimited by biological reproduction, in ways that produce and reproduce colonial violence. Part three unpacks Fanon's theory of colonial fascism through colonial race warfare. Part four shows how Fanon's articulation of Pan-Africanism and the African Legion constitute an anti-colonial anti-fascism that repositions the question of life itself.

CANGUILHEM AND THE BIOPOLITICS OF FASCISM

It is unclear whether Fanon ever met Canguilhem. Nonetheless, Fanon makes explicit his debt to Canguilhem's work in *Black Skin, White Masks*. While unpacking the failure of psychoanalysis to travel to the colonial situation, Fanon remarks that a homology between the family and the nation exists. "A normal child brought up in a normal family will become a normal adult. There is no disproportion between family life and the life of the nation."¹⁰ Fanon, sensing his reader's protest about his invocation of "normality" turns to Canguilhem: "let us refer them to the extremely instructive work by G. Canguilhem, *Le Normal et Le Pathologique*, though it focuses solely on the biological. Let me just add that in the psychological field the abnormal is he who demands, appeals, and begs."¹¹ We turn here to *The Normal and the Pathological* before unpacking Fanon's debts to Canguilhem.

The Normal and the Pathological was written as Canguilhem's PhD dissertation, which he defended in 1943. It was subsequently published in multiple editions, first in that same year and then again in 1950, and then in 1966 with an introduction by Michel Foucault. As Foucault notes in his introduction, the central problematic of Canguilhem's text is a biopolitical one. Canguilhem is trying to ascertain the relationship of life and death to the life sciences.^{12,13} In Canguilhem's own words, his attempt to uncover the meaning of the pathological is directly related to "concrete human problems" at the "crossroads of several sciences."¹⁴ The problem of the pathological in medicine structures both somatic nosology, bodily diseases, and physiological pathologies that emerge in relation to bodily diseases. Canguilhem's inductive conclusion and the guiding thread of his investigation is that "there is not in itself an a priori ontological difference between a successful form and an unsuccessful form."¹⁵ Rather, Canguilhem's thesis is that instead of the normal determining what is pathological, it is the pathological; the error and difference excluded from the domain of life that structures the normal. Just as the norm is constituted by error

in the life sciences, so too does Canguilhem's investigation proceed through a history of errors, without a single historical origin.¹⁶

Canguilhem's "reflective origin" takes us through the history of science from Hippocratic medicine through the nineteenth century, from Auguste Comte to Bernard, up to Canguilhem's own present moment, where he engages with Jacob von Uexküll, Henry Ey, and Kurt Goldstein. All these figures were also central to Fanon's training and thought.¹⁷ For Canguilhem, these figures provide a genealogy of the pathological and the normal that maps onto a relationship between life and death, health and disease. Canguilhem begins by diagnosing and distinguishing between what he calls an "ontological" conception of disease and a dynamic conception. For Canguilhem, an ontological conception of disease is based on responding to a "therapeutic need" that can be restored back to a norm.¹⁸ The ontological conception of disease aims to conquer disease, and in the process to "reassure ourselves" against the anguish that "we expect nothing good from nature itself."¹⁹ The ontological conception of disease that constructs itself in response to this anguish defines pathology as something that can be localized, defined, and resolved through technical means. The norm is restored by elevating the human above nature.

On the other hand, Canguilhem traces a dynamic conception of disease, first in Ancient Greece, and then later in contemporary vitalism. A dynamic conception of disease sees nature (physis) and man as intertwined in harmony and equilibrium. Disease is a disturbance of this harmony. Rather than disrupting a norm, however, the discordance of disease is seen as generating a "new equilibrium in man."²⁰ Pointing to the Greek idea of the pharmakon, Canguilhem argues that, for the Greeks, disease and cure are also intertwined. Disease is understood as a "reaction designed to bring about a cure; the organism develops a disease in order to get well."²¹ Here the faith of medicine is not a faith in man's capacity to elevate themselves over nature.

Where these two conceptions of disease converge, however, is a conception of war and battle at the heart of disease. Presaging Foucault's insights, Canguilhem articulates a consistent historical theme in the relationship of the pathological to the normal, which is "either a battle between the organism and a foreign substance [the ontological], or an internal struggle between opposing forces [the dynamic]."²² Canguilhem's theorization of the relationship between the pathological and the normal in medicine and biology as of antagonism and battle, is at the heart of his metapolitical intervention. Offering these two conceptions of biological battle, Canguilhem articulates a politics of life premised on pacification and potentially genocidal eradication on the one hand, and an affirmative biopolitics on the other.²³

For Canguilhem, the development of positivism in the nineteenth century, is key.²⁴ Canguilhem draws on and engages with the work of the French physician Francois-Joseph-Victor Broussais, his disciple Bégin, the Scottish physician Scott Brown, and the French physiologist Claude Bernard.²⁵ But it is his engagement with August Comte that lays out his understanding of the relationship between the normal and the pathological, and life and death, in modernity. Comte

solidifies the idea that the pathological state derives from a normal one. Disease and death are, for Comte, a result of pathologies, deviations from the norm, resulting from irregular excitations.²⁶ This conceptual relationship between the normal and the pathological ties directly to Comte's positivist method. The understanding of the pathological is based on a prior norm, but at the same time, the scientific study of pathology reveals scientific laws about what constitutes the normal. This method, in turn, reifies this conception of the normal and the pathological as a dogmatic truth.

For Canguilhem, the attempt to circumscribe the pathological in relation to the normal through positivism is also an attempt to circumscribe life with direct political implications. As Canguilhem argues, to define the pathological and the abnormal as a deviation from an otherwise steady and scientifically provable law, is to deem the abnormal as less than valuable. Despite Comte's claims to a value-free science, the normative and norm converge.^{27,28} Comte's politics mirrors this conception of health, by equating political order to a norm, and political crises to a disease. In Comte's conception of politics, progress is necessary, but also necessarily subordinated to order where "incurables" will "subside into the social nullity suited to their mental and moral nature."²⁹ As Canguilhem argues, Comte's language of incurable is not accidental. For Comte, political crises, like a disease, require societies to be brought back to an essential and unchanging structure, "tolerating progress only within the limits of variation of the natural order defined by social statistics."³⁰

In this sense, Canguilhem's theory of the relation of the pathological to the normal as one of antagonism and battle takes on a new light. Canguilhem argues that an image of thought bound by an ontological conception of the normal and the pathological redistributes who is available for premature death—for Comte's "incurables" become an existential threat to the health of the body politic. Later Canguilhem will describe the ontological and positivist definition of the normal as a theology that defines pathology as evil incarnate. Through its association with death, the abnormal takes on an ontological status akin to evil itself. By defining disease as an evil that is antithetical to life itself, Comte, and the ontological conception of disease more generally, enables the justification of any number of indiscriminate violences in the name of health.³¹

As Robert Esposito notes, these philosophical reflections on the normal and the pathological, written in 1943, are indissociably connected to Canguilhem's own milieu of Vichy France, and were part of a metapolitical commentary on Nazism. This anti-fascist commentary is best articulated through Canguilhem's association with institutional psychotherapy and Tosquelles, whom Fanon also worked alongside a decade after Canguilhem.³² A year after Canguilhem defended *The Normal and the Pathological*, In the words of David Macey, Canguilhem "was involved in an undertaking against death at Saint-Alban," where he was awarded the Croix de la Resistance for treating wounded resistance fighters for several weeks in 1944.³³ Here Canguilhem worked explicitly against the eugenic vision of life in Nazi Germany and Vichy France, which allowed 40,000 psychiatric patients to die over the course of the war.³⁴ Canguilhem's

brief stay at Saint- Alban was transformative for both Canguilhem and for institutional psychotherapy. Canguilhem was transformed from a pacifist into a committed anti-fascist. Institutional psychotherapy, in turn, took on Canguilhem theoretical insights as they would later be elaborated in *The Normal and the Pathological*. As Camille Robcis argues, institutional psychotherapists followed Canguilhem to consider psychosis a “variation of the normal, another form of life” instead of a deviation that was opposed to life.³⁵ This formed a cornerstone of institutional psychotherapy’s political and historical analysis of medical research as well as the idea that this research presupposed an ideal of normativity.³⁶

Canguilhem’s friendship with institutional psychotherapists was premised on a philosophy of resistance and rupture to fascism in a way that resonates with Fanon’s radicalization of anti-fascism in the colonial context. Institutional psychotherapists rethought the world and the clinic as a space of collective fantasy that often reinforced and consolidated existing social hierarchies. These social hierarchies often emerged from direct experiences of the encampment and incarceration of institutional psychotherapists under fascist regimes. Rather than being an “irrational” aberration from liberal society, fascism was an expression of mass desire that reflected libidinal investment in these hierarchies.³⁷ Tosquelles named this relationship between individual alienation and collective fantasy, between micropolitical and macropolitical investment in social hierarchies, as “concentrationism” or “le-tout-pouvoir.”^{38,39}

For Esposito, Canguilhem’s entire project in *The Normal and the Pathological* can be characterized as an engagement with, and a genealogy of, fascist concepts of biology and life.⁴⁰ Canguilhem, for his part, traces this genealogy from the deployment of social statistics in Comte’s positivism, through eugenics. The invention of social statistics marks a technology that can measure the norm through the concept of the average in populations.⁴¹ This culminates, for Canguilhem, in the eugenic projects of Galton, through biometric applications anatomy. Comte’s reduction and delimitation of life to a norm equated with a universal law, easily transposes itself into a delimitation of life to a “higher race.” The definition of what constitutes “life” is thus reduced to a norm equated with the biological reproduction and health of certain members of the human species. The ontological definition of the normal and the pathological is more than a war against a foreign substance that threatens the organism: It is a race war that operates by defining and delimiting a conception of life itself, and the diseased as antithetical to that life.⁴² The war against these threats will have to be waged aggressively to ensure the body politic’s health—up to the point of genocide.

FANON AND THE FAMILY

Fanon's invocation of Canguilhem, while limited to the footnote described above, emerges at a key moment in *Black Skin, White Masks*. Pace Lewis Gordon, *Black Skin, White Masks* is a descent through the zone of non-being, into a "veritable hell" that mirrors Dante's descent through the *Inferno*.⁴³ The Canguilhem's reference appears after Fanon's encounter on a train with a boy who turns to his mother after seeing Fanon, saying repeatedly "Look! A Negro!" Fanon is radically disoriented, his corporeal-body-schema collapses, and his sense of self is stripped away. In this scene Fanon experiences his own pathologies in relation to a white norm. The pathology emerges from an aspiration to be something that the Black man fundamentally cannot be: First, because the white man will never allow the black man to be fully recognized as human, which is to say, white; second, because the white man's very sense of whiteness, of what it means to be fully human, is constituted through violence, desire, and fear of the Black man. In this sense, the pathological nature of the Black man to be recognized as white, is suicidal in its "lactification."⁴⁴ Throughout we get the sense that the Black person who desires to be white is sick and in need of a cure.

By the time we arrive at Canguilhem we have emerged from the suffocating embers of Fanon's own delirium. Here Fanon begins to diagnose, in both the medical and philosophical sense, his own pathology and attempt to discover a "cure." Fanon reworks the relationship between the normal and pathology to reframe the very terms on which he has been operating thus far throughout his study. For Fanon, psychoanalysis fails to travel to the colonial world. Indeed, Fanon has already previewed some of these failures in a dialogue with *The Psychology of Colonization* by M. Mannoni. As a psychoanalyst, Mannoni's sin is that he attempts to reduce the pathologies of the colonized to familial determinations, and attempts to trace the pathologies of the Malagasy to childhood trauma. These familial determinations leave the colonized stuck between two undesirable options for "normality": Either they accept their inferiority in relation to the father/colonizer, or they recognize their dependence on him. For Fanon, in the colonial situation, Freud's "discoveries of are no use whatsoever."⁴⁵

After experiencing his own form of madness, Fanon returns to this dialogue with psychoanalysis, this time armed with a reference to Canguilhem. Here Fanon argues that the very understanding of the normal and the pathological in psychoanalysis is colonial and flawed because it builds its analysis through familial determinations: "Psychoanalysis—and this can never be stressed enough—sets out to understand a given behavior within a specific group represented by the family."⁴⁶ Fanon begins, perhaps surprisingly, by arguing that psychoanalysis makes sense only in the European context.⁴⁷ For Fanon, psychoanalysis makes sense in a European society because European society is modeled on the family. At every level from the family to the nation, society is built through patriarchal hierarchies: "In Europe and in every so-called civilized or civilizing country the family represents a piece of the nation. The child leaving the family environment finds the same laws, the same principles, and the same

values.”⁴⁸ For Fanon, Freud and Mannoni are correct to begin with the family as their unit of analysis because contemporary European society is modeled on the patriarchal family and the authority of the father. But they are incorrect to assume that this model of the family, and thus the insights of psychoanalysis, are transhistorical and transcultural. Rather, a racist, patriarchal society allows psychoanalysis to flourish.

Fanon reconstitutes the relationship between the normal and the pathological by drawing on Canguilhem. The homology between the family and the nation in Europe society produces “normal” individuals: “A normal child brought up in a normal family will become a normal adult.”⁴⁹ It is here that we get the footnote that we set out to unpack at the outset of our investigation. Fanon exhorts his reader not to misunderstand him for invoking the idea that the European child is the model of normality. He then invokes Canguilhem in response to the imagined and rhetorical question: “What do you mean by the normal?”⁵⁰ Fanon is alerting us to the fact that by “normal” here, he does not mean to reify a conception of a norm. Though Fanon is preoccupied with the normative implications of the idea of the normal, he does not endorse them as they are established here. Rather, as we argued above, the idea of what constitutes the “normal” is produced by a racist and patriarchal social formation. Second, in a colonial, capitalist, and patriarchal society, the pathological is constituted in reference to, and as a derivation of, the normal. The normal that Fanon is invoking here is, in Canguilhem’s philosophical vocabulary, an “ontological” conception of the normal. By holding up Europe as an eternal model for what constitutes a normal and healthy civilization, non-European societies are deemed diseased and pathological. Their failure to live up to the European norm, and to imbibe the normative values of liberal humanism and the bourgeois family, provides a ready-made description for thinkers like Mannoni, who read an inferiority complex into the colonized. That is why, for Fanon, it is the “racist who creates the inferiorized,” or, we might say, the pathological.

We can see this relationship between the normal and the pathological elsewhere in Fanon’s writings, and in the clinical practice Fanon derived from his association with Tosquelles and the institutional psychotherapists. *Black Skin, White Masks* was written and published before Fanon’s stay in Saint-Alban and his work alongside Tosquelles. Fanon’s residency at Saint-Alban post-dated his medical school training at Lyon, where *Black Skin, White Masks* was written as his (rejected) medical thesis. It is thus likely that Fanon was thus exposed to Canguilhem’s thought, and Canguilhem’s influence precedes his intimate familiarity with institutional psychotherapy.⁵¹ Nonetheless institutional psychotherapy likely affirmed and materialized Fanon’s affinity for Canguilhem and gave Fanon the tools to make Canguilhem’s abstract archeology concrete. Fanon himself would then radicalize the insights of both Canguilhem and Tosquelles in his anti-colonial politics and his own psychiatric practice in Blida-Joinville.

In Fanon’s reading of the North African Syndrome, for example, Fanon notes how the European standard of the human “normal” produces an inhuman

pathology.⁵² Where French doctors explain this in terms of a racial pathology that deviates from the colonial norm, Fanon shows this pathology is less an encounter between a primitive and a civilized society, and more the effect of a colonial imposition of a French standard: “They have had France squeezed into them wherever, in their bodies, and in their souls.”⁵³ The solution, for Fanon, thus involves a transformative clinical practice that aims to reconstitute the very relationship between the normal and the pathological. Fanon’s clinical practices of institutional psychotherapy in France and Algeria involved transforming the clinic by instituting Arab cafes, playing football with patients, and creating a newspaper that the patients themselves were tasked with running.⁵⁴ Modeled on the ship’s log, Fanon hoped that this newspaper would embody a clinical practice that would create a new normal for his patients, by providing them with a means of community and communication.⁵⁵ The practical work of the clinic, as the “healing collective” was for Tosquelles and for Fanon and Canguilhem, a space of anti-fascist resistance.⁵⁶ Transforming the social environment of the clinic into a space to interrogate power in macro and micropolitics was key to the therapeutic and political space of the clinic.⁵⁷ Reducing the suffering of patients through meetings, unions, libraries, journal clubs, newspapers, film, and sport would also enable the emergence of “alternative, less hierarchical, and less oppressive social relations.”⁵⁸ Fanon’s exposure to institutional psychotherapy at Saint-Alban likely inspired Fanon’s clinical practice as a form of revolutionary politics and “social integration through group work.”⁵⁹ Here Fanon practiced institutional psychotherapy through work with patients on a collective newspaper, plays, and musicals.⁶⁰ For Nica Siegel, institutional psychotherapy “gave Fanon his first clinical tools to unsettle the regnant school of colonial psychiatry.”⁶¹ If the “North African Syndrome” is a product of colonialism, then the solution, Fanon implies, is decolonization.

Fanon would concretize his analysis of the relationship between the normal and the pathological and colonial patriarchy in *L’an V de la Révolution*, a collection of essays that would be printed in English as *A Dying Colonialism*. In this text, Fanon elaborates a political critique of patriarchal colonial fantasies as “normal.”^{62,63} For Fanon, the colonial obsession with the veil is a necessary invention of a European society that attempts to order its colony and make sense of a society that it imagines as pathological in relation to itself. Fanon argues that the colonizer needs the veil to unify the perception of “Algerian feminine society” that “tolerates no modification, no variant... with the veil, things become well-defined and ordered.”⁶⁴ Fanon outlines how this understanding of the veil is rooted in an explicit colonial project to “bring about the disintegration” of Algerian society.

This project centered on the ethnographic and sociological invention of Algeria as a supposedly “matrilineal society.”⁶⁵ For the colonizer, women played an essential role in winning over Algerian society to the colonial project. The crux of this project was to impose a “normal” colonial patriarchy on a pathological Algerian society that hid women behind the veil: “The dominant administration solemnly undertook to defend this woman, pictured as

humiliated, sequestered, cloistered... It described the immense possibilities of woman, unfortunately transformed by the Algerian man into an inert, demonized, indeed dehumanized object.”⁶⁶ Where a pathological matrilineal Algerian society (“medieval and barbaric”) had dehumanized the Algerian woman, the normal, patriarchal European society would redeem her through the total “domestication” of Algerian society.⁶⁷ Read in this way, that Fanon inverts the project of colonial redemption in the language of “domestication” is not incidental—the family is central to the political struggle over the future of Algeria, and as a model for colonial rule.

For Fanon, the family became a site of literal warfare: The besieging of Algerian women, and the “combat” to control them, constituted the “pivot of Algerian society.”⁶⁸ This warfare took place in schools and in workplaces, as sites that meant to constitute a “disciplined” colonized subjectivity. Schools for “young Moslem girls” to be trained in Western values proliferated. For Fanon, this training was the training of “‘developed’ natives” who “are the commandos who are entrusted with destroying the cultural resistance of a colonized country.”⁶⁹ While these “developed” natives are situated on the frontlines of a cultural war, they are nonetheless eternally dependent on the European. Illustrating the ultimately patriarchal and authoritarian basis of a colonial society, Fanon’s takeaway is that “integration, in order to be successful, seems indeed to be simply a continued, accepted paternalism.”⁷⁰

Here it is important to note that Fanon is neither for nor against the veil, nor does he attempt to undermine the political history of it. Rather, Fanon illustrates the colonial politics of the veil in the situation of the Algerian Revolution. Here the veil is deemed pathological by colonial society, so the colonized react by attempting to protect an aspect of their culture. Fanon argues this most apparently, and interestingly by paralleling his understanding of the role of the veil in Algerian society to negritude. Fanon argues that both negritude and the veil are part of a “reactive” phase of revolutionary struggle, where the new men and women of the revolution have not yet been birthed, and the “plans of the occupier” determine and shape the strategies of resistance. Fanon argues “is the white man who creates the Negro. But it is the Negro who creates negritude. To the colonialist offensive against the veil, the colonized oppose the cult of the veil.”⁷¹ In this initial phase of the struggle, the veil formed a key part of maintaining cultural autonomy and pushing back the colonizing impositions of the patriarchal norm. Fanon thinks this is a necessary beginning to revolutionary struggle, but not its end point. Later we will see how Fanon articulates an alternative to negritude’s “reactionary” vitalism through a revolutionary vitalism.

In a colonial fascist society, patriarchal paternalism is always underwritten by collective fantasies produced through colonial violence. This lesson Fanon shares with both Canguilhem and Tosquelle’s institutional psychotherapy, but Fanon “radicalizes” this thought in a colonial situation. Fanon shows how the “normal” European obsession with the veil is predicated on sadistic fantasy and sexual violence. The fantasy of “unveiling” the Algerian women to “order” her

into colonial society is always accompanied by rape and abject humiliation—“straight off, with the maximum of violence, there is possession, rape, near-murder.”⁷² Fanon emphasizes that brutality and sadism of this fantasy is doubled by the fear of the woman who screams and struggles before being ripped apart. European society deems itself normal through its patriarchy, and Algerian society perverse and pathological through its matrilineal society and practice of veiling. The rape fantasies of the “normal” colonizer extend this pathologizing of the Algerian women: “The Algerian woman becomes hypocritical, perverse, and even a veritable nymphomaniac.”⁷³

Ultimately, for Fanon, colonialism must accept the limits of its patriarchal terms of control or drive itself to a genocidal madness. The telos of this “delirious” Manicheism, like Canguilhem’s analysis of biopolitics, is genocide: “One cannot say that a given country is racist but that lynchings or extermination camps are not to be found there. The truth is that all that and still other things exist on the horizon. These virtualities, these latencies circulate, carried by the life-stream of psycho-affective, economic relations...”⁷⁴

With Canguilhem, Fanon reverses the relationship between the normal and the pathological. For Fanon, the white norm, and all of European society, are pathological. More than just a simple reversal, this reconfiguration of the normal and the pathological reconstitutes their meaning. Racism is normal in the sense that it occupies an ontological conception of the norm that reifies the normal and delimits a conception of life. But it is also pathological in its own delimitation, producing anxieties and anguish structured around colonial violence. The European norm, modeled on the patriarchal family, refuses to accept any openness towards the future, any form of life, that deviates from it. It is hellbent on freezing them in time through petrification and cultural mummification, and of destroying them through genocidal conquest. Reading Fanon alongside Canguilhem returns us to a theory of fascism.

FANONIAN FASCISM

Scholars often identify the 1970s as an era where a more capacious theory of fascism emerged, divorced from historical fascisms of Nazi Germany and Italy. Building off the praxis of the Black Panther Party Black radicals, George Jackson and Angela Davis theorized fascism as the expansion of a racialized carceral society that was rooted in chattel slavery.⁷⁵ In Europe, Deleuze and Guattari’s *Anti-Oedipus* theorized fascism as a ubiquitous form of desire in any oedipal and capitalist society. Michel Foucault identified fascism with biopolitics, and the making live and letting die of racial populations. Placing Canguilhem in dialogue with Fanon reveals a much older tradition of this form of theorizing—one that stretches back to colonial Vichy France, one that radiates beyond Canguilhem and Fanon themselves—that sees fascism as an orientation towards life itself. For Canguilhem, Fanon, and the institutional psychotherapists that they were in dialogue with, fascism was the production of a specific form of collective desire, rather than a historically specific social formation. A fascist group fantasy

pathologizes certain forms of life as an existential threat that must be eradicated and transforms this eradication into a passion.⁷⁶

Fanon built on this European tradition of thought and placed it in dialogue with anti-colonial theorists to theorize the Algerian War as a form of colonial fascism. Aimé Césaire's *Discourse on Colonialism* famously argued that fascism was nothing more than a "boomerang" effect of colonialism; that prior to European fascism, European colonialism was already practicing fascism in the colonies. For Césaire colonialism is evidence that European civilization is a sick and already fascistic civilization. Through a surrealist poetics, Césaire demonstrates this is a unconscious desire that is built into the project of "the West" itself; that "the whole edifice of Western, Christian civilization in its reddened waters, it oozes, seeps, and trickles from every crack."⁷⁷ Demonstrating the roots of fascism in chattel slavery, Césaire describes, colonial fascism as a process of "thingification" or, in Senghor's words, that it "devitalizes" everything it touches. Negritude, on the other hand, is a vital force that draws on the historical memory of the past to open a new future.⁷⁸ Suzanne Césaire draws, as Aimé does, on the anthropologist Leo Frobenius. Césaire distinguishes between an Ethiopian civilization that carries a story of vital energy, and a Hamitic civilization that urges to dominate.⁷⁹ Working with these traditions of thought, Fanon charts out his own theory of fascism as an orientation towards life.⁸⁰

For Fanon, the emplotment of myth, methods of popular violence, auto-suggestion and affective contagion produced in "delirious crowds," the reliance on the Father figure of De Gaulle brought into power by a "coup," colonial massacres, and the willingness to wage a war in Algeria towards a genocidal end, all produce a situation that Fanon names "fascism."⁸¹ Begüm Adalet has recently argued that Fanon is a multiscalar thinker. Following Adalet, Fanon's theory of fascism works through a similar multiscalar politics. If we take Fanon's debts to Canguilhem seriously, we can trace Fanon's theory of fascism from the distribution of the normal and the pathological across the social life of the colony, through institutional psychotherapy's analysis of affect, fascist drives, group fantasy, and institutions produced in an atmosphere of popular violence, to a global structure of Western complicity with colonial fascism that builds off Caribbean theorizing fascism as a project of Western civilization. This theory of fascism is not linear; instead the fascist orientation towards life that emerges through the distribution of the normal and the pathological is produced as the simultaneity of this multiscalar colonial fascist violence.

For Fanon, fascism is not a boomerang effect of colonialism.⁸² Rather, for Fanon, colonialism is fascism, because colonialism is race war against life itself. By rethinking the relationship between the pathological and the normal through colonialism, Fanon thus also provides a counterweight to Canguilhem's Eurocentric analysis of fascist biopolitics. This argument begins to unfold in the very passage we have just analyzed where Fanon engages with Canguilhem. The West's support for fascist regimes is not an aberration. For Fanon, all Western

society models the nation on the family, and on the rule of the father.⁸³ Returning to this passage, it seems clear that Fanon is talking about the fascist nature of European society in these terms all along. The reason the family structure and the national structure are closely connected is because “Militarization and a centralized authority in a country automatically result in a resurgence of the father’s authority.”⁸⁴ Written in 1952, as Europe was still recovering from World War II, it is impossible to mistake Fanon’s invocation of the militarized father. It is possible that Fanon, aware of the anti-fascist context of Canguilhem’s own work, is trying to rework our understanding of fascism. This emerges most clearly as Fanon analyzes race war through colonial combat in Algeria.

Fanon revises his account of race war by moving his account of “delirious Manicheanism” from a psychopolitical argument in *Black Skin*, to a structural account of the spatial politics of colonialism in *Wretched*.⁸⁵ Here Fanon shows how the idea of the colonial “normal” is produced through colonial warfare that makes the colonized into a pathologized enemy. His account centers the “murderous and decisive struggle between the two protagonists,” the colonial power and the colonized, who meet each other with a reciprocal force and violence in

combat.⁸⁶ What Fanon had earlier described as petrification—the colonizer freezing the colonized in time—he re-describes as an effect of the spatial division of the colony, that he traces from the urban division of streets to global capitalism. The dividing line between who lives and who dies emerges from valorizing certain forms of racialized life over others:⁸⁷ Fanon’s emphasis on the creation and imposition of racial difference through a species creating violence, and Canguilhem’s biopolitical fascism: “For it is the settler who has brought the native into existence and who perpetuates his existence. The settler owes the fact of his very existence, that is to say his property, to the colonial system.”⁸⁸

The colonial norm must be maintained at all costs, and colonialism must be defended. In this articulation of the normal, the norm is iterated as both a vital defense of a healthy body politic, and an ethical injunction of the values of Western liberalism: “He is the corrosive element, destroying all that comes near him; he is the deforming element, disfiguring all that has to do with beauty or morality; he is the depository of maleficent powers, the unconscious and irretrievable instrument of blind forces.”⁸⁹ The violence of the colonized who fight for freedom is pathologized as both a threat to public health and the as the definition of evil itself. Western values imagine themselves as “diseased” and “poisoned” by contact with the native. The native forms an inscrutable mass, a horde, a “breeding swarm” with “distended bodies which are like nothing on earth, that mob without beginning or end.”⁹⁰ This diseased threat is cosmological; it threatens the very fabric of the universe, and thus calls for a warfare of extermination that can be driven to genocide: “That is why we must put the

D.D.T. which destroys parasites, the bearers of disease, on the same level as the Christian religion which wages war on embryonic heresies and instincts,

and on evil as yet unborn.”⁹¹ Like Canguilhem, he sees this process as a fascist expression of the “totalitarian character of colonial exploitation.”⁹²

Second, Fanon builds a revised account of where the normal and the pathological emerge from by working through and revising institutional psychotherapy’s account of group fantasy, and the micro and macro-politics of fascism in the process. Echoing institutional psychotherapy’s analysis of group fantasy and the “delirious crowds” that swept de Gaulle back into power, Anglo-America is driven more by an “obsessional dream” of colonial fascism than any concrete analysis of the political conjuncture. For Fanon, the relationship between the normal and the pathological is a product of colonial warfare. Colonial warfare produces a “pathology of atmosphere” that extends from the metropole to the colony, effecting the psyche of both settlers and the colonized. The real fantasies of these combatants are effects of the colonial situation, and ultimately the violence that radically transforms subjectivities towards the reproduction of that violence. The pathology of atmosphere in the colony produces fantasies enabling the colonizer to imagine their violent pacification, and genocidal combat, as peaceful: “he shows them up and puts them into practice with the clear conscience of an upholder of the peace; yet he is the bringer of violence into the home and into the mind of the native.”⁹³ The colonial norm, like Canguilhem’s analysis of Auguste Comte’s positivism, assumes itself a transhistorical law and essence that extends into an indefinite future. For Fanon, “Colonialism... is not satisfied by this violence against the present.”⁹⁴ The Manichean structure of colonialism generates fantasies of the colonized as frozen in time, requiring the permanent tutelage of the white race: “The history of the colonized peoples is transformed into meaningless unrest.”⁹⁵

Collective colonial fantasy is mirrored by the violent practices of colonialism itself. For Fanon, the “pathology of atmosphere” also produces warfare as a popular, mass affair. The cycle of violence begetting violence in the colony parallels fascism in the strategies and tactics through which it conscripts popular violence towards maintaining an eternal colonial norm. Popular violence begins a spiral of reciprocal kinetic exchange, fueled by blood debt.⁹⁶ Fanon locates the rape fantasy of unveiling Algeria in the history of French conquest, the burning of villages, the taking of property, the pillaging of farmlands, and the rape of women.^{97,98} The war targets the Algerian civilian population; “every Muslim is a rebel” became an official “policy of genocide.”⁹⁹ In both *Wretched of the Earth* and writings for the F.L.N. journal *El Moujahid*, Fanon recounts the arming of the *pied noirs* into a paramilitary police force. Lacoste armed nearly 80,000 colonizers, “made up of congenitally racist and fundamentally immoral men who feared the revolutionary movement and were first to fix a quasi-genocidal character on the repression,” in a bid for “total surface control” of the Algerian cities and countryside.¹⁰⁰ Reproducing in *Wretched* an article published in *Resistance Algerienne*, Fanon notes how Governor-general Robert Lacoste armed French civilians and encouraged them to “fire on any person who seems to him a suspect.”¹⁰¹ The French settlers responded with enthusiasm, and assumed the roles of militia man, soldier, and police officer. Civilians were

tasked with checking on surviving Algerians, responding to “terrorism,” tracking suspects, and killing runaways.¹⁰² From this decree in 1956 to create urban and rural militias, the Algerian War was fueled as much by popular violence and mass slaughter as it was covert police action and torture.

Fanon, quoting the author of the article, endorses its conclusion: “Fascist militias, they’ve been called. Yes; but on the individual level, on the plane of human rights, what is fascism if not colonialism when rooted in a traditionally colonialist country?”¹⁰³ Fanon demonstrates how the normal and the pathological are a product of colonial warfare. Here Fanon’s theory of fascism extends to show how popular violence and the pathological fantasies of a colonial fascist norm are co-constitutive. They facilitate the death of the colonized in the name of defending the health of the colony against the pathologies that threaten it, galvanizing an entire population around genocide.

For Fanon, the dreamwork of fantasy elaborates the idea that a colonial/fascist idea of freedom is synonymous with this erotic sadism. This history of colonialism is repeated in the present context of the Algerian War through colonial massacres. For Fanon, the ritualized violence of the colonial massacre performs a psychic function—one that he identifies as instilling a colonial assurance and hope amongst the *peuplades*. This enables liberals who had previously downplayed their racism to give into their race fantasies and recover “their old ignorance, their traditional contempt.”¹⁰⁴

Fanon anticipates arguments parallel with current readings of fascist freedom in the “West” based on the right of a “superior” race to create its own right and law of conquest.¹⁰⁵ They also echo Klaus Fuchs’s psycho-sexual reading of fascism as a response to the “Judeo-Bolshevik” “Red Flood”—a violent feminine threat to masculinity. The flow embodies both the thrill and the terror that masculinity might be undone: “Bolshevism, the Red Army—all of these under the leadership, or with the decisive participation of women. Female practice: to do what is forbidden.”¹⁰⁶ Against these flows—of rivers, of blood, of filth—the soldier must dam oneself, to protect the masculine body against dissolution. This damming is affirmed through rituals of violence that culminate in an annihilation of the enemy—the only permissive flow of blood that purifies and protects the self while enabling the forbidden desire of violence to flow. Fanon exposes how the European “normal” that is predicated on pathologizing other forms of life through similar forms of damming, produces its own pathological violence. As Fanon argues: “the act assumes a para-neurotic brutality and sadism, even in a normal European.”¹⁰⁷

Fanon repositions Canguilhem’s theory of fascist biopolitics through the colony by also extending the analysis of fascism from a philosophical investigation into biology to a geopolitical analysis of global politics.¹⁰⁸ This solidarity extends globally, for Fanon, as all the colonial powers of the West line up to support France against decolonization movements, “rushing headlong into the swearing-in ceremony of fascism.”¹⁰⁹ These countries, in their own bid to maintain colonial power over world politics, support ultra-colonialism’s bid to integrate French Algeria through violent warfare. Colonial power tends towards fascism,

for Fanon, as each of these powers takes stock of the possibilities of a decolonized world order.¹¹⁰

Colonial fascism is a product of the transnational circulation of materials, goods, arms, settlers, and soldiers from the metropole to the colony and back again. Global capitalism, threatened by Communism and anti-colonialism alike, fuels fascism in the colony:¹¹¹ “[F]ascism and colonialism are intrinsically linked.”¹¹² Like Canguilhem, Fanon builds a theory of fascism that operates through logics of colonial life and anti-colonial death, which maps onto an understanding of the normal and the pathological. For Fanon, the colonial normal is a fascist logic, upholding the law of father, the family, and the colony as an eternal value that extends into an indefinite future. It sees any potential movement against this norm as a violent pathology that threatens the health of the body politic, and justifies violence to defend colonialism, up to the point of genocide. By resituating Canguilhem’s theory of race war, and the production of the normal and the pathological, in colonial warfare in Algeria, Fanon reverses the relationship between the normal and the pathological. The colonial normal, constitutive of the violent “pathology of atmosphere” that saturates the colony is pathological in its war against the future and its war against life. It conscripts both the settler and European masses into popular violence against those who threaten it.

“THE ABNORMAL IS HE WHO DEMANDS, APPEALS, AND BEGS”

Fanon, pace Canguilhem, also articulates an affirmative biopolitical theory of anti-fascism, that by necessity will also be anti-colonial. Canguilhem develops his affirmative biopolitics and anti-fascist philosophy of life through his engagement with vitalist philosophy and science. Rather than upholding the idea of the normal as an eternal law that the pathological threatens, Hippocratic philosophical, medical, and biological vitalist conceptions view the normal and the pathological on a continuum of life and death. For Canguilhem, pathology is not opposed to life; rather it is better seen as a modification of life, “of being really another way of life.”¹¹³ Through von Uexküll and Goldstein, Canguilhem argues that the normal is constituted through an organism’s milieu, the phenomenological world and their environment that they are a part of, rather than any stable organic state.¹¹⁴ For Canguilhem, the payoff of resituating the normal and the pathological in the milieu, is to reverse the order of priority. Every “normal” situation is a product of a prior pathology, a prior attempt of an organism to adapt to a new milieu: “Insofar as the animal living being ultimately reveals itself to have been a mutant at first tolerated and then invasive, the exception becomes the rule, in the statistical sense of the word.”¹¹⁵ Through this extension of vitalism, Canguilhem reverses the relationship between the normal and the pathological. For Canguilhem, what is understood as pathological in the “ontological” conception of health and disease, is, in fact the “normal” creative process of lively organisms. The pathological,

rather, than being opposed to life, is life. The pathological, and what Canguilhem will later understand as the “monstrous” is the capacity of life to constantly invent itself anew, to generate creative difference from the present: “[F]or us a living species is viable only to the extent that it shows itself to be fecund, that is, productive of novelties, however imperceptible these may be at first sight.”¹¹⁶ In the present, health is determined by the milieu’s capacity to sustain life. But life is also constituted by the capacity of an organism to adapt to a future different from the present. Canguilhem’s vitalist revaluation of the pathological, with its Bergsonian and Nietzschean debts, thus also affirms life and creative difference over and against the eugenic politics of fascism. Canguilhem, like contemporary forms of New Materialism, tries to build an affective appreciation for the creativity of life itself as part of his anti-fascist politics.¹¹⁷

As I have argued from the outset, placing Canguilhem into conversation with Fanon is not intended to make Fanon derivative of Canguilhem. What this conversation instead reveals is a structure of thought that Canguilhem and Fanon share. As Édouard Glissant argues, Fanon’s thought is nomadic and creolizing—it draws from the specific context of Fanon’s anti-colonial journey—from Martinique, to France, to Algiers, to Tunis, and throughout Africa—to combine different modes of thought into a new form.¹¹⁸ Earlier I emphasized how Fanon paralleled his interpretation of the veil with his analysis of negritude as a “reactionary” phase of anti-colonial struggle. Here it is worth extending that analysis to think through the content of Fanon’s anti-fascist vitalism.

Both Césaire and Leopold Senghor, the two anti-colonial politicians and philosophers most associated with a vitalist *négritude*, were known to Fanon. Césaire, from Martinique, was famously one of Fanon’s schoolteachers in the lycée, and Fanon cites Senghor across his writings. As recent scholarship has demonstrated, both Césaire and Senghor also articulated a vitalist politics that drew on French philosophical thought—mainly Henri Bergson and African spiritual and philosophical thought.¹¹⁹ In “*Négritude: A Humanism of the Twentieth Century*,” Senghor draws on a scientific and philosophical revolution within Europe—quantum physics, relativity, wave mechanics, the uncertainty principles—to demonstrate how mechanical determinism had been superseded. For Senghor, this was a philosophical and political revolution, because it revealed the relational and energetic nature of the cosmos—one that enabled the creation of both the new and free will. For Senghor, this realization within European was preceded by the philosophical thought of Africans, who imagine the world as a “fundamentally mobile, yet unique, reality that seeks synthesis.”¹²⁰ Senghor’s God, like Spinoza’s, is an immanent force that “vitalizes and devitalizes all other beings, all the other life forces.”¹²¹ Cheik Thiam names this an “Afri-centered conception of time” of becoming—where past, present, and future are linked in the same relation of birth, death, and renewal.¹²² Elsewhere, Senghor calls for integrating European process philosophy, including Marxian dialectics, with “Negro-African methods of knowledge” to articulate a particularly African socialism.¹²³ The Césaires turn to surrealism and the

unconscious as a means of both diagnosing and recovering a vital sense of self. While the Césaires insists on a new future, Aimé Césaire's work especially also tends towards a romantic vitalism, and the restoration of natural unity in a future time. Fanon takes sustenance and inspiration from the Césaire's and Senghor's analysis of colonial fascism, their vitalism, and their Pan-Africanism. At the same time, though, he resists their "reactive" tendencies. For Fanon, it is only the revolution itself, the people united in a dynamic movement, that can overcome colonial fascism.

After invoking Canguilhem to assure his reader that he must not be misunderstood as invoking the idea of the normal in relation to the European family, Fanon continues in his own name, to modify Canguilhem's positive revaluation of the pathological and the abnormal. Fanon writes, "[L]et me just add that in the psychological field the abnormal is he who demands, appeals, and begs."¹²⁴ Fanon's paradigmatic example of the potentially abnormal European child is the child of thieves and bandits. Here Fanon emphasizes the importance of the figure of the criminal and the beggar in his thought, as they constitute the abnormal that gives coherence to the European family as the normal. But as the outcasts of European society, their demand, and their appeal, reveals the pathologies present in the colonial constitution of the norm.¹²⁵ The protests lodged by those who beg are a protest against the colonial social order itself. Their failure to adapt to the colonial milieu reveals the petrification of a colonial order. Their madness, monstrosity, pathology, and abnormality try and open a living future in their cry of protest. Fanon opens the pathological and the abnormal in a way that mirrors Canguilhem. The abnormal beggar is the embodied expression of life itself: the capacity to "introduce invention into existence" against a stultifying colonial fascism.

Throughout his writings, Fanon rewrites the position of the beggar and the criminal within colonial economies of violence. The criminal plays an essential, if understudied role in Fanon's analysis of madness in the last chapter of *The Wretched of the Earth*. After analyzing a series of case studies that shows the ways in which colonial combat produces mental disorders in both the colonizers and the colonized, Fanon challenges the French psychiatric explanation for pathology—that the "normal African is a 'lobotomized European.'"¹²⁶ The idea that the "normal African" is a pathological deviation from the "normal" European emerges as an explanation for crime—"the transcription into the nature of his behavior of a given arrangement of the nervous system."¹²⁷ This ascription emerges from doctors, the state, and the police, who together produce the real of the normal and the pathological.¹²⁸ Fanon affirms the abnormality of the criminal in relation to the European but does so to mark the dynamic movement of revolutionary struggle. The Algerian revolutionary struggle itself, as a dynamic movement, restages the problem of the crime from one of deviant people to a question of the relationship between persons and the state within colonial history. The existence of crime is in indication that the colonial state itself is pathological in violence.¹²⁹ Fanon remarks that a radically new form of crime,

one that is not directed inward towards the Algerian people, but outward against the colonizer, also marks a new stage in revolutionary struggle and the recognition of “true protagonists.”¹³⁰

Those familiar with Fanon’s work will immediately associate the beggar and criminal with the lumpenproletariat, the collective, anti-colonial (and anti-fascist) subject of *The Wretched of the Earth*. In the eyes of the colonizers, the national parties, and the proletariat, the lumpen are the abnormal to the colonial norm: the colonial system that secures itself over and against these peasant and criminal masses. The national parties and colonized proletariat view the lumpen in terms of a reactionary pathology within the revolution: “They show a whole range of characteristics—individualism, lack of discipline, liking for money and propensities towards waves of uncontrollable rage and deep discouragement which define a line of behavior that is objectively reactionary.”¹³¹ Fanon, satirizing the statistical aggregation of the norm, notes how the landless peasants are imagined by the proletariat as “vital statistics” and “insoluble problems” before they come to the city.¹³² But, echoing Canguilhem’s own reevaluation of the pathological as life itself, the lumpenproletariat emerge for Fanon as a life-creating force, a vitalist counter to the fascist atmosphere of death in the name of the normal that saturates the colony. For the lumpen, the settler is “the death of aboriginal society, cultural lethargy, and the petrification of individuals. For the native, life can only spring up again out of the rotting corpse of the settler.”¹³³

We see this process most clearly in *A Dying Colonialism*, where Fanon articulates the primary goal of his essays as illustrating that a “new society has come to birth. The old Algeria is dead. All the innocent blood that has flowed on to the national soil has produced a new humanity.”¹³⁴ For Fanon, a new humanity is birthed through a revolutionary struggle that the “West” names as a pathological deviance for normal European life. This struggle challenges the norms of Western patriarchy, but also revolutionizes the Algerian family itself.

For Fanon, the question of undoing the patriarchal familial is not resolved in dialogue, but through the process of anti-colonial revolution itself. Fanon argues “in the practice of the Revolution the people have understood that problems are resolved in the very movement that raises them.” Women take on a new role, and a new “dialectic of the body and of the world,” through their revolutionary activity. Sons begin to lead their fathers in a revolutionary movement, and the hierarchy of elder sons is upended.¹³⁵ Fanon articulates this in ways that echo Canguilhem as the creation of new norms: “[T]he person is born, assumes his autonomy, and becomes the creator of his own values.”¹³⁶ Whereas prior to the revolution having daughters who reached puberty and did not marry was seen to “prolong an abnormal situation,” the revolution itself creates new forms of sociality where “men’s words were no longer law” and the Algerian woman “literally forged a new place for herself by sheer strength” (*italics in original*).¹³⁷ Marriage itself gives way to a new form of revolutionary love.¹³⁸ The lumpen unravels the fascist structure of the family, and generates life where colonialism produced death, cultural mummification, and petrifica-

tion. In other words, the lumpen are key to creating a living milieu in the present that is open to a dynamic future through fighting literature. The lumpen are Fanon's vitalist response to the petrifying effects of the colonial-fascist norm.

A PAN-AFRICAN FUTURE TO COME

The lumpen, however, are just the starting point of Fanon's vital anti-colonial and anti-fascist politics. Colonialism fascism is a global problem. Fanon thus restages the problem of nation and violence, and revolutionary vitalism once again, this time on a global scale. As a diplomat, Fanon attempted to accentuate an emergent collective solidarity amongst the Third World—one that placed the African continent at the center of world struggle. As Nica Siegel argues, Fanon scales desire and disalienation through an ideal of Pan-African solidarity. For Siegel this is part of a militant therapeutic politics that extends Fanon's clinical practice to a world scale. We build on this analysis by pointing out the anti-fascist reorientation of the normal and the pathological through a voluntary African Legion. In an exhortation for unity and solidarity amongst African peoples, Fanon writes that "The African peoples must likewise remember that they have had to face a form of Nazism, a form of exploitation of man, of physical and spiritual liquidation clearly imposed, that the French, English, and South African manifestations of that evil need to engage their attention, but they must be prepared also to face this evil as an evil extending over the whole of the African territory."¹³⁹ Explicitly paralleling the European experience of fascism with the colonies, Fanon writes: "We Africans say that for more than 100 years the life of 200 million Africans has been life at a discount, contested, a life perpetually haunted by death."¹⁴⁰ If for Fanon, fascism is a global colonial race war against life, anti-fascism requires a global, anti-colonial response that affirms life even within a movement of revolutionary violence. For Fanon, this process is one that necessarily mobilizes people for the work of decolonial warfare enacted by a collective people for the process of "the giving birth of a world."¹⁴¹

For Fanon, this birth takes the form of an African Legion: A volunteer people's army to defend the continent, directly countering the popular violence of colonial fascism. In many ways, this ideal is the culmination of Fanon's thought, expressing his Pan-Africanism through a vision of a new people emerging from a war against colonialism. This idea emerged from a series of conversations culminating in the All-African Peoples Conference (Fanon calls this the first Congress of African peoples) in Accra in 1958.¹⁴² The Conference's slogan echoed was a Pan-African twist on the Communist Manifesto: "Peoples of Africa, Unite! You have nothing to lose but your chains! You have a continent to regain! You have freedom and human dignity to attain! And to the Colonialists we say! Hands off Africa! Africa must be free!!"¹⁴³ According to the Africa Special Report on the conference, the Congress's resolution for an African Legion called for an army of "volunteers who will be ready to protect the freedom of the African peoples."¹⁴⁴ Through decolonial violence, the people's army

would create a new African, a new human, a new collective subject, and a new form of life in the world. Where the Algerian lumpen still bore the psychological scars of combat and war, an African people's army could wash away these wounds and death's perpetual haunt. The African Legion enacts the possibility of displacing colonial pathologies and creating a new norm in the African to come. For Fanon, the African Legion opens the future, not in the terms of the "mechanically inevitable," but in the terms of "revolutionary commitment" and "combat." The African Legion affirms a future that says, for Fanon, "Under these conditions, yes, we can be optimistic."¹⁴⁵

Notes

1. Frantz Fanon, "Racism and Culture," in *Toward the African Revolution* (Grove Press, 1967), 40.
2. Fanon, "Racism and Culture," 40-41.
3. Achille Mbembe, *Critique of Black Reason* (Duke University Press, 2017), 2.
4. David Marriott, *Whither Fanon?* (Stanford University Press, 2018), 15.
5. Frank Wilderson, *Red, White, and Black: Cinema and the Structure of US Antagonisms* (Duke University Press).
6. Frantz Fanon, *Black Skin, White Masks* (Grove Press, 2008), 133.
7. Robert Bernasconi, *The Racial Politics of Life Itself: Goldstein, Uexküll, Canguilhem, and Fanon* (Rowman & Littlefield International, 2015). The *Care of Life: Transdisciplinary Perspectives in Bioethics and Biopolitics*, 121-133 is the only text that I have been able to uncover that places Canguilhem and Fanon in dialogue on the question of biopolitics. In this text Bernasconi focuses more on Canguilhem's own (problematic) debts to Jacob von Uexküll and his refusal to engage with fully engage with the implications of racism and colonialism. His engagement with Fanon is limited to two paragraphs. This essay, by contrast, foregrounds Fanon.
8. Stuart Elden, *Canguilhem* (Cambridge University Press, 2018), 9.
9. This essay was written before Israel's genocidal war against Palestine accelerated in October 2023. As many have argued, and as a Fanonian analysis would also reveal, this process began much earlier than October 2023, and stretches back, at the very least, to the Nakba of 1948. Israel's practices and collective fantasies of violent settler colonialism are the clearest illustration that what Fanon describes as colonial fascism is still present and intensifying in contemporary society. The "Manichean" structure of a colonial society, violently and spatially organized between the colonizer and the colonized, symbolized most clearly by the Apartheid wall; the collective myths of ethno-racial superiority that deems Palestinian life pathological and thus "necessary" for extermination so that "Israel" can continue to exist; the eros and passion that accompanies this exterminatory violence; the methods of popular violence that are a structure of settlement in the West Bank; the collective popular violence that stops aid trucks in order to make Palestinians starve; the exterminatory violence that aid sites enable; the cult of Netanyahu; but also the liberal complicity with genocide that sees the problem begin and end with

Netanyahu (for Fanon this genocide would be not a problem of reclaiming Israeli's "democracy," but a typical expression of Israeli's democracy); the complicity of the "West" with the genocide—both as it attempts to crush anti-colonial desire and through the direct supplying of weapons; the violent and repressive policing of any movement that attempts to stop that genocide; the refusal to sanction any right of resistance, to deem it mad, pathological, and antithetical to civilization itself. The real hope and possibility that anti-colonial struggle itself might reconfigure desire and an orientation towards life on a global scale.

10. Fanon, *Black Skin*, 121.
11. Fanon, *Black Skin*, fn. 121.
12. Michel Foucault, "Introduction," in Georges Canguilhem, *The Normal and the Pathological* (Zone Books, 1989), 22.
13. We should also note that many scholars have pointed out that Foucault's own genealogy of race war and biopolitics is indebted to Canguilhem's *Normal and the Pathological*. See Maria Muhle, "A Genealogy of Biopolitics: The Notion of Life in Canguilhem and Foucault," In *The Government of Life* (Fordham University Press, 2014), 77-97.
14. Georges Canguilhem, "The Normal and the Pathological," in *Knowledge of Life* (Fordham University Press, 2008), 34.
15. Canguilhem, "The Normal and the Pathological," 31.
16. Canguilhem, "The Normal and the Pathological," 63.
17. David Macey, *Frantz Fanon: A Biography* (Verso Books, 2012), see chapter four especially.
18. Canguilhem, "The Normal and the Pathological," 39.
19. Canguilhem, "The Normal and the Pathological," 40.
20. Canguilhem, "The Normal and the Pathological," 40-41.
21. Canguilhem, "The Normal and the Pathological," 40-41.
22. Canguilhem, "The Normal and the Pathological," 41.
23. Canguilhem, "The Normal and the Pathological," 126.
24. Canguilhem, "The Normal and the Pathological," 43.
25. Elden, Canguilhem, 28.
26. Canguilhem, "The Normal and the Pathological," 48.
27. Canguilhem, "The Normal and the Pathological," 56.
28. Canguilhem, "The Normal and the Pathological," 56.
29. August Comte, *System of Positive Polity: Third Volume*, (Burt Franklin, 1876), xv.
30. Canguilhem, "The Normal and the Pathological," 64.
31. Canguilhem, "The Normal and the Pathological," 104.
32. I am deeply indebted to an anonymous reviewer for pointing to this connection and encouraging elaboration on this point.
33. David Macey, "The honour of Georges Canguilhem," *Economy and Society* 27, no. 2-3 (1998): 171-181.

34. Camille Robcis, *Disalienation: Politics, philosophy, and radical psychiatry in postwar France*. (University of Chicago Press, 2021), 33. Macey, "Canguilhem," 176.
35. Robcis, *Disalienation*, 3.
36. Robcis, *Disalienation*, 36, 38.
37. Robcis, *Disalienation*, 12.
38. Robcis, *Disalienation*, 2-3.
39. Gilles Deleuze and Félix Guattari, *Anti-Oedipus: Capitalism and Schizophrenia* (Penguin Books, 2009), 176.
40. Robert Esposito, *Bios: Biopolitics and philosophy* (University of Minnesota Press, 2008), 189.
41. Canguilhem, "The Normal and Pathological," 151.
42. Across his writings, Canguilhem gives hints towards, but never fully unpacks, the implications of Nazism for a metapolitics of colonialism, racism, and slavery. In the *Normal and Pathological*, for example, Canguilhem protests equating the European "norm" with the Black norm. Examining different rates of hypoglycemia in Africans, Canguilhem warns against equating of the high rates of hypoglycemia in Black populations with pathology. Canguilhem argues that Europeans transform this data in a pathology to service a racial hierarchy. The European norm is held up as a normative value, and the high rates of hypoglycemia are equated with African "indolence." In a later lecture on the relationship between the machine and the organism, elaborates this theme of racial hierarchy in relation to the normal and the pathological. Here he argues that this concept of the norm is at the heart of humanism itself. Canguilhem argues that the attempt to regulate life and delimit through normal through a machinic humanism, is structured by its subjugation of the animal and the slave. Turning to Aristotle, and then Descartes, Canguilhem argues that the founding gesture of humanism is to elevate the Human above both the animal and the slave. The machine emerges as a paradigm for Descartes by devaluing the animal: "Descartes does to the animal what Aristotle did to the slave: he devalorizes it in order to justify its use by man as an instrument." For Canguilhem, the category of the Human assumes its status as the separate and distinct master of nature by denying purpose to extra-Human nature and reducing the animal and slave both to a pure means. Ultimately, this justifies and legitimates Descartes "construction of a mechanical model of the living body, including the human body" and modern Humanism more generally.
43. Lewis R. Gordon, *What Fanon said: A philosophical introduction to his life and thought* (Fordham University Press, 2015); Fanon, *Black Skin*, xii.
44. Fanon, *Black Skin*, 29.
45. Fanon, *Black Skin*, 84.
46. Fanon, *Black Skin*, 120.
47. Here it's important to note that Fanon doesn't think that colonialism is solely responsible for patriarchy, nor does he think that pre-colonial societies don't have their own "norms" that structure social life in authoritarian and hierarchical ways. For example, Fanon notes throughout *A Dying Colonialism*

that the father is “the authority for all things, the founder of every value,” and that, due to the agrarian basis of society, the male “enjoys an almost lordly status” as the inheritor of this role and the land. What makes European patriarchy different is the violent imposition of patriarchy as a model of rule that distributes the normal and the pathological throughout colonial society. Algerian patriarchy may be violent and repressive but it is not a colonial imposition (with the specific nature of colonial violence that Fanon’s theory brings to the table). What’s different and specific about the imposition of European patriarchy is how it imposes itself as a colonial form of life that deem other forms of life as pathological in ways that are not reducible to political economy. This difference is also illustrated by Fanon’s initial failures at Blida-Joinville and his reflections and reevaluations, where he attempted to introduce European cultural life into the Algerian clinic. Part of what Fanon is doing in this passage is also demonstrating the misapprehension of a French colonialism that invented Algerian society as a matrilineal society, and to disabuse European society of the specialness of its patriarchy. Written for a French audience, *A Dying Colonialism* illustrates that the authority of the European father is no more pre-ordained than that of the Algerian father. The “origins” of patriarchy can be explained through political economy, but the specific form of European patriarchy and its distribution of the normal and the pathological through colonial imposition is a psychic-sociogenic relation that Fanon thinks requires the most thought to unravel. In this respect, for Fanon the return to pre-colonial “tradition” is neither a viable nor a desirable response to this imposition. In *Wretched*, Fanon will articulate how the initial phases of the revolution are marked by fantasies of anti-colonial violence, that are often channeled into internecine violence between the colonized.

48. Fanon, *Black Skin*, 121.
49. Fanon, *Black Skin*, 121.
50. Fanon, *Black Skin*, fn. 121.
51. Macey, *Fanon: A Biography*, 146-147.
52. Frantz Fanon, “The North African Syndrome,” in *Toward the African Revolution* (Grove Press, 1967), 3.
53. Fanon, “North African Syndrome.”
54. Nancy Luxon, “Fanon’s Psychiatric hospital as a Waystation to Freedom,” *Theory, Culture & Society* 38, no. 5 (2021): 93-113; Nica Siegel, “Fanon’s Clinic: Revolutionary Therapeutics and the Politics of Exhaustion,” *Polity* 55, no. 1 (2023): 7-33.
55. Frantz Fanon, “Our Journal,” in *Alienation and Freedom* (Bloomsbury, 2018), 314-315.
56. Robcis, *Disalienation*, 40.
57. Robcis, *Disalienation*, 46.
58. Robcis, *Disalienation*, 6.
59. Keller, Richard, *Colonial Madness: Psychiatry in French North Africa* (University of Chicago Press, 2019), 181.
60. Robcis, *Disalienation*, 60-61.

61. Siegel, "Fanon's Clinic," 13.
62. Fanon's first essay, titled "Algeria Unveiled," has been interpreted as essentializing gender, fetishizing the body of Algerian woman, de-historicizing the dynamic political history of the veil, and diminishing the agentic capacity of Algerian women as dependent on men. See Anne McClintock, "Fanon and Gender Agency," in *Rethinking Fanon: The Continuing Dialogue* (Rowman and Littlefield, 1999).
63. Important recent interventions have challenged these interpretations; see Drucilla Cornell, "The secret behind the veil: A reinterpretation of 'Algeria Unveiled'," *Philosophia Africana* 4, no. 2 (2001): 27-36. Here we might gain some clarification by placing Fanon in dialogue with Canguilhem. The various interpretative impasses of Fanon's essay are unmasked when we read Fanon's essay as inhabiting and then unraveling the European "normal" in a colonial situation.
64. Frantz Fanon, *A Dying Colonialism* (Monthly Review Press, 1965), 36.
65. Fanon, *A Dying Colonialism*, 37.
66. Fanon, *A Dying Colonialism*, 38.
67. Fanon, *A Dying Colonialism*, 38-39.
68. Fanon, *A Dying Colonialism*, 38-39; see also Patricia Owens, *Economy of Force: Counterinsurgency and the Historical Rise of the Social* (Oxford University Press, 2015).
69. Fanon, *A Dying Colonialism*, 38-39.
70. Fanon, *A Dying Colonialism*, 44.
71. Fanon, *A Dying Colonialism*, 47.
72. Fanon, *A Dying Colonialism*, 48.
73. Fanon, *A Dying Colonialism*, 48.
74. Fanon, "Racism and Culture," 41.
75. Alberto Toscano, *Late Fascism: Race, Capitalism, and the Politics of Crisis*
76. (Verso, 2023), 32.
77. Guattari argues that "All fascist meanings stem out of a composite representation of love and death, of Eros and Thanatos now made into one," see Felix Guattari, *Chaosophy* (MIT Press, 1995), 168-169.
78. Aime Césaire, *Discourse on Colonialism* (Monthly Review Press, 2000), 36.
79. Césaire, *Discourse*, 52; Wilder, *Freedom Time*, 182.
80. Suzanne Césaire, "Leo Frobenius and the Problem of Civilizations," in *The Great Camouflage: Writings of Dissent (1941-1945)* (Wesleyan University Press, 2012)
81. As an inspiration for the Black Panther Party, and as an institutional psychotherapist himself working with a "French" philosophical tradition, Fanon thus both anticipated, and likely inspired both streams of anti-colonial, anti-fascist theorizing of the 1970s.
82. Frantz Fanon, "Ultracolonialism's Rationale," in *Alienation and Freedom*
83. (Bloomsbury, 2018), 602.
84. The most famous argument here is Hannah Arendt's *The Origins of Totalitarianism* (Houghton Mifflin Harcourt, 1973).

85. This marks another difference between Fanon's analysis of patriarchy in Europe and Fanon's analysis of patriarchy in the Algerian family
86. Fanon, *Black Skin*, 120-121.
87. Begüm Adalet, "Infrastructures of Decolonization: Scales of Worldmaking in the Writings of Frantz Fanon," *Political Theory* 50, no. 1 (2022): 5-31.
88. Fanon, *Wretched*, 28.
89. Fanon, *Wretched*, 31.
90. Fanon, *Wretched*, 28.
91. Fanon, *Wretched*, 32.
92. Fanon, *Wretched*, 33.
93. Fanon, *Wretched*, 32.
94. Fanon, *Wretched*, 32.
95. Fanon, *Wretched*, 29.
96. Frantz Fanon, "Why We Use Violence," in *Alienation and Freedom*
97. (Bloomsbury, 2018), 654.
98. Fanon, "Why We Use Violence," 654.
99. Fanon, *Wretched*, 56.
100. Fanon, *Dying Colonialism*, 45.
101. Frantz Fanon, "The Strategy of an Army with It's Back to the Wall," in
102. *Alienation and Freedom* (Bloomsbury, 2018), 593.
103. Fanon, "The Strategy of an Army...", 593.
104. Frantz Fanon, "The Cavalry of a People," in *Alienation and Freedom*
105. (Bloomsbury, 2018), 620.
106. Fanon, *Wretched*, 71.
107. Fanon, *Wretched*, fn. 72.
108. Fanon, *Wretched*, fn. 71.
109. Fanon, *Dying Colonialism*, 56.
110. Toscano, *Late Fascism*, 51; Tyler Stovall, *White Freedom: The Racial History of an Idea* (Princeton University Press, 2021)
111. Klaus Theleweit, *Male Fantasies, Volume 1: Women, Floods, Bodies, History* (University of Minnesota Press, 1997), 403. See also Robyn Marasco, "There's a fascist in the family: Critical theory and antiauthoritarianism," *South Atlantic Quarterly* 117, no. 4 (2018): 791-813.
112. Fanon, *Dying Colonialism*, 46.
113. Frantz Fanon, "The Western World and the Fascist Experience in France,"
114. in *Alienation and Freedom* (Bloomsbury, 2018), 608.
115. Fanon, "The Western World...", 607-608.
116. Fanon, "The Western World...", 608.
117. But for Fanon, fascist violence, the affective pathologies and fantasies of the colonizer, and the state of war in the colony are not reducible to capitalist logics of converting money into more money. Capitalism, for Fanon, while it requires genocidal warfare to establish itself, is wary that the continuation of this warfare will disrupt the "political stability and calm social climate" necessary to maintain profit. Waging colonial warfare through popular violence, has especially dire consequences, Fanon argues, as the colonies are

transformed into markets for colonial goods (Wretched, 51). In contemporary colonial capitalism, colonial warfare threatens the point of consumption as much as the point of production. Colonial fascism thus operates according to its own logics of the normal and the pathological, and of life and death, up to the point of choking off its own capitalist fuel for the sake of continuing violent warfare against the colonized. The settler population is not merely manipulated as a tool of colonial capital. Indeed, in Fanon's account of de Gaulle's rise to power, it is as much the power of the crowds themselves that carry him into leadership, as it is any objective change in the material conditions of colonialism. The popular fascism of settler colonialism, swept up in its own genocidal violence, will also turn on its leaders if they are seen as betraying the cause. This happened in January of 1960, during the "week of Barricades" where pied noirs staged an insurrection, as the army and police watched on, believing that De Gaulle had betrayed the settler cause, and again, in December of 1960, when the settlers refused to let De Gaulle enter Algeria. For Fanon, the point of this popular violence was to maintain "a system of social violence such as exists in fascist countries and places where barbarism prevails" (Alienation and Freedom, 665). Ultra-colonialism's fascist rationale accelerates its genocidal violence to the point of suicide.

118. Fanon, "Ultra-Colonialism's Rationale," 605.
119. Canguilhem, "The Normal and the Pathological," 89.
120. Canguilhem, "The Normal and the Pathological," 70.
121. Canguilhem, "The Normal and the Pathological," 127.
122. Canguilhem, "The Normal and the Pathological," 125.
123. Canguilhem, "Aspects of Vitalism," 72. See for example, William E. Connolly, *Aspirational Fascism: The Struggle for Multifaceted Democracy under Trumpism* (University of Minnesota Press, 2017).
124. Édouard Glissant, *Poetic of Relations* (University of Michigan Press, 1997), 18.
125. Donna V. Jones, *The Racial Discourse of Life: Negritude, Vitalism, and Modernity* (Columbia University Press, 2010); Gary Wilder, *Freedom Time: Negritude, Decolonization and the Future of the World* (Duke University Press, 2015); John Drabinski, *Glissant and the Middle Passage: Philosophy, Beginning, Abyss* (University of Minnesota Press, 2019). There is some disagreement amongst these texts over whether Negritude's vitalism constitutes a "reactive" tendency in thought that relies on some form of essentializing and reifying race (Jones), whether Negritude's vitalism is, in fact, future oriented and open in ways that are similar to Fanon's in its expression of freedom (Wilder), and somewhere in between (Drabinski). While this author is most sympathetic to Wilder's analysis of Negritude as a future-oriented vitalism, Fanon often read Negritude as a "reactive" project. For Fanon this reaction was less a problem of biological essentialism, and more a necessary but radically insufficient moment in the revolutionary movement towards freedom. Fanon thus likely took the dynamic and transformative aspects of Negritude's vitalism, while situating them in revolutionary struggle itself.

126. Léopold Sédar Senghor, "Negritude: A Humanism of the Twentieth Century," in *Colonial Discourse/ Post-Colonial Theory*, eds. Patrick Williams and Laura Chrisman (Columbia University Press, 1994), 27-35, 30.
127. Senghor, "Negritude: A Humanism...", 30.
128. Thiam Cheik, *Return to the Kingdom of Childhood* (Ohio State University Press, 2014), 6.
129. Senghor, Léopold Sédar, *On African Socialism*, trans. Mercer Cook (Frederick A. Praeger, 1964), 75.
130. Fanon, *Black Skin*, fn. 120.
131. In a lecture delivered in Tunis in 1959 or 1960, entitled the "Meeting Between Society and Psychiatry," Fanon argued that "The mad person is one who is 'foreign' to society. And society decides to rid itself of this anarchic element. Internment is the rejection, the side-lining of the patient. Society asks the psychiatrist to render the patient able again to reintegrate into society. The psychiatrist is the auxiliary of the police, the protector of society against ... The social group decides to protect itself and shuts the patient away" (*Alienation and Freedom*, 518).
132. Fanon, *Wretched*, 244.
133. Fanon, *Wretched*, 245.
134. Fanon, *Wretched*, 246.
135. See Delio Vásquez, "Illegalist Foucault, Criminal Foucault," *Theory & Event* 23, no. 4 (2020): 935-972 for the best exposition of this argument on criminality through Foucault.
136. Fanon, *Wretched*, 247-248.
137. Fanon, *Wretched*, 88.
138. Fanon, *Wretched*, 88.
139. Fanon, *Wretched*, 73.
140. Fanon, *Dying Colonialism*, 27-28.
141. Fanon, *Dying Colonialism*, 104.
142. Fanon, *Dying Colonialism*, 101.
143. Fanon, *Dying Colonialism*, 107, 109.
144. Fanon, *Dying Colonialism*, 115.
145. Frantz Fanon, "Unity and Effective Solidarity are the Conditions for African Liberation," in *Toward the African Revolution* (Grove Press, 1967), 171.
146. Fanon, "Unity and Effective Solidarity," 174.
147. Frantz Fanon, "This Africa to Come" in *Toward The African Revolution*
148. (Grove Press, 1967), 181.
149. George Houser, *No One Can Stop the Rain* (Pilgrim, 1989), 70-72.
150. Pan Africanism Today Secretariat. "African Liberation Day: The Enduring Struggle against Colonialism and Capitalism." *Peoples Dispatch*, May 25, 2020. <https://peoplesdispatch.org/2020/05/25/african-liberation-day-the-enduring-struggle-against-colonialism-and-capitalism/>.
151. "Special Issue on All-African's People's Conference at Accra: People's Conference Plan's Permanent Body," *Africa Special Report* 4, no. 2 (1959).
152. Fanon, "Unity and Effective Solidarity,"